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In-Cognitive: A web-based Python application for fuzzy cognitive map design, simulation, and uncertainty analysis based on the Monte Carlo method

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ABSTRACT

Fuzzy Cognitive Mapping is a semi-quantitative modelling method, widely used for decision support in various domains. However, existing software applications have been criticised over inadequate handling of uncertain information, lack of accessibility, and inability to converge to solutions for all modelled systems. Here we present In-Cognitive, an open-source, web-based application for the creation, visualisation, and simulation of Fuzzy Cognitive Maps, ensuring solution convergence and allowing for Monte Carlo uncertainty analysis. The application is built in Python and Bokeh and provides an accessible and user-friendly interface to model various systems quickly and reliably and evaluate the robustness of the modelling solutions.

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Support email for questions

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1. Motivation and significance

Fuzzy Cognitive Maps (FCMs) are graphs consisting of nodes and edges, altogether providing a semi-quantitative representation of a system. FCMs are often used to support stakeholders in system understanding and relevant decision making across diverse domains such as energy, medicine, and manufacturing [1–3]. Nodes represent a concept of the cognitive framework associated with the system and the edges represent causal relationships between nodes. A number within $[-1, 1]$ is assigned to each edge, indicating the degree (weight) of influence between the interconnected nodes. If C_i and C_j are the interconnected nodes, the weight w_{ij} indicates the influence of C_j over C_i . The node values, A_i , are derived from the FCM simulation, which is based on the iterative equation Eq. (1).

$$A_i^{k+1} = f(x_i^k) = f\left(\sum_{j=1, j \neq i}^n (w_{ij}A_j^k + d_iA_i^k)\right). \quad (1)$$

A_i^k and A_i^{k+1} are the values of the C_i node at k th and $(k + 1)$ th iteration, parameter d_i indicates the correlation of C_i with its past values, and the f function is a transfer function used to squash the A_i^k values within $[0, 1]$ or $[-1, 1]$. It should be noted that there are alternatives to the activation function of Eq. (1) in the literature, such as in [4] (for a review see [5]). However, Eq. (1) is a generalised form of the widely established activation functions, as it allows to represent Kosko's original activation rule [6], (optionally) modified to account for a node's historic values [7], with or without weights (d_i). Typically, two transfer functions are used in the FCM literature, the sigmoid and the hyperbolic tangent (\tanh) functions ((2)–(3), respectively). In both transfer functions, parameter λ is a design parameter that is applied universally to all FCM nodes.

$$f_s = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-\lambda x)} \quad (2)$$

$$f_h = \frac{\exp(\lambda x) - \exp(-\lambda x)}{\exp(\lambda x) + \exp(-\lambda x)} \quad (3)$$

There exist several FCM software implementations. FCM Modeller was among the first simulation tools in the FCM literature [8], followed by a series of more advanced software in terms of graphics and user interfaces [9–11], technical capabilities [12–14], and design capabilities [15–18]. However, none of these applications allowed flexibility to define parameter λ , with most of them assuming $\lambda = 1$. The problem with FCMs based on these transfer functions is that the convergence of Eq. (1) is not always guaranteed [19–22]. A sufficient but not necessary condition for the FCM simulation to converge is that parameter λ lies within certain bounds [19,20]. Thus, the assumption that $\lambda = 1$ may constrain the FCM convergence and solution rate.

A second limitation associated with existing FCM applications lies in their accessibility. Apart from a few exceptions [23–25], the vast majority of the available software are either closed solutions (e.g., [15]) and web applications (e.g., [26]) or developed in proprietary platforms, such as MATLAB (e.g., [17]).

Third, much like the FCM framework itself, these applications have been criticised over their capacity to handle uncertain information [27]. There have been attempts to handle uncertainty via manual configurations based on diverse transfer functions and parameters to identify common patterns in the results [28], as well as by introducing probabilistic uncertainty distributions. However, such endeavours have not been integrated in FCM software solutions and/or have resulted in additional optimisation requirements [29] and losses in stakeholder input. Monte Carlo (MC), a prominent method for uncertainty analysis, has been

found promising in similar fields, such as fuzzy agent-based modelling [30] or linguistic information-driven multi-criteria decision aid [31]. However, MC simulations remain largely untested in the FCM domain [32,33], and thus unavailable in existing FCM tools.

In this paper, we introduce the In-Cognitive application to address all three gaps. First, the software introduces and optimises the value of parameter λ [21], allowing the investigation of responses and inferences from cognitive systems that reach indefinite or chaotic behaviour. Second, In-Cognitive is a fully open-source and open-access Python application. Third, it allows for Monte Carlo simulations to analyse the impact of uncertainty perturbations in both input values and weights (MCFCM hereafter), notably coupled with the λ selection of [21] to avoid iterations of indefinite or chaotic node responses. In-Cognitive has been successfully used for stakeholder engagement on the energy sector of Greece [34] and Italy [35] and for analysing the perspectives of different experts in terms of the capabilities of models for climate change mitigation [33]. In Table 1, we summarise the information on the gaps identified in the FCM application literature.

2. Software description

2.1. Software architecture

In-Cognitive is written in the Python programming language and based on the Bokeh Python library. As Fig. 1 shows, In-Cognitive consists of a client-side (front-end) Graphical User Interface (GUI) and a Bokeh-Tornado web server (back-end). The front-end and back-end exchange data via GUI widgets and queries, triggering server-side Python modules that deploy all features and procedures described in Section 2.2.

The user can configure the FCM layout through the tables in the 'Inputs' panel (Fig. 2). Alternatively, the user can configure the FCM layout using an xlsx file of predefined format (opening primarily with Microsoft Excel but also with OpenOffice and other spreadsheet applications). We have selected this Excel file format to enable user friendliness and simplicity. Right after the definition of the FCM layout, the user can set the parameters of the FCM simulation (e.g., the transfer function) and the MCFCM procedure in the second GUI subpanel (bottom and left side of Fig. 2). After specifying all these parameters and pressing the execution button, a core Python dictionary, the 'fcm_layout_dict', is filled out and sent to the server. The 'fcm_layout_dict' is then read by the Python modules of the back-end code (see Section 2.2 for more details). After the execution of this code, results are sent back to the browser and illustrated in the 'Results' panel (Fig. 2). The Bokeh framework automatically creates all required HTML, CSS, and JavaScript code to ensure user interaction. However, it is possible to change the default HTML and CSS through the files stored in the 'static' and 'template' folders of the code repository.

2.2. Software functionalities

Functionalities are divided into two sections: (a) GUI-side functionalities and (b) server-side functionalities. The former section consists of (i) FCM layout creation, (ii) MCFCM parameter configuration, and (iii) results plotting; while the latter consists of (i) input Excel parsing, (ii) transfer function configuration, (iii) FCM simulation, and (iv) MCFCM simulation.

FCM layout creation

To create an FCM network, the user can modify the two tables on the 'Inputs' panel or upload an input Excel file via a button on the top right side of the 'Inputs' panel (featuring a 'Choose file' prompt). The 'xlparse' module then parses the input Excel file and returns the 'fcm_layout_dict' dictionary. As shown in Fig. 3, the

Table 1

Overview of available FCM software applications and their openness, flexibility to define transfer function parameters, and capacity to analyse uncertainty.

Application	Language	Openness	Transfer functions	Flexibility over λ	Uncertainty or robustness
FCM Tool [9]	N/A		Binary, trivalent, sigmoid		Learning (particle swarm optimisation)
FCM Expert [10]	Java	Accessible	Binary, saturation, trivalent, tanh, sigmoid	Sigmoid (via learning)	Learning (particle swarm optimisation, differential evolution, real-coded genetic algorithm, variable mesh optimisation)
ISEMK [11]	N/A		N/A		Learning (structure optimisation genetic algorithm)
FCM Designer [12]	Java		Binary, saturation, trivalent, sigmoid		
FCM-Analyst [13]	Java	Accessible	Flexible		
Mental Modeler [15]	Web	Accessible (after query)	N/A		
JFCM [16]	Java	Accessible	Binary, bipolar, sigmoid, tanh, Gaussian, Cauchy	Sigmoid	Learning (non-Hebbian learning algorithm)
ESQAPE [17]	MATLAB	Accessible	Sigmoid, tanh		
FCMPy [23]	Python	Open source	Binary, trivalent, sigmoid, tanh	Sigmoid	Learning (non-linear Hebbian learning, active Hebbian learning, real-coded genetic algorithm)
FCM Wizard [24]	Web (PHP, CSS, JavaScript)	Accessible (after query)	Sigmoid		Learning (Hebb-based learning algorithms)
In-Cognitive	Python	Open source	Sigmoid, tanh	Definition or optimisation of sigmoid, tanh	Monte Carlo simulations (MCFCM)

Fig. 1. Software architecture.

file consists of three worksheets and should contain the nodes along with their initial values, interconnections, weights, correlation lag, and whether they are input or output nodes. Defining initial values allows users to perform what-if scenario analyses via FCMs [36], to see how different 'interventions' introduced into the system affect the end state of its components. Additionally, the 'auto weights' setting in the fourth column of Fig. 3a sets the degree of correlation of each node's current value with its past value. If 'auto weights' are non-zero, the 'auto lag' setting on the

fifth column defines the lag between the node's current and past value (see [17]).

When the user provides an input, In-Cognitive visualises the input data in a circular layout (Fig. 4). The input nodes are positioned to the left of the plot and shown with a red colour, while the output nodes are positioned to the right side and shown with a green colour. The lines connecting the nodes (edges) are colour-coded based on the weights between the nodes they connect. The darker the colour of a line, the closer the weight is to the

Fig. 2. Graphical User Interface.

Fig. 3. The input Excel file, showcasing the three required worksheets and filled with data from the illustrative example in Section 3.

maximum weight value of one. The exact value of the weight is shown when the user hovers their mouse over a line.

Configuration of simulation parameters

After editing the FCM topology, users can specify the simulation parameters (left side of the 'Results' panel in Fig. 2) and, specifically, whether they prefer to introduce variation on the

input nodes and/or the weights. Users can specify the standard deviation (SD) of this variation, which corresponds to the SD of the Beta distribution. If the 'Weights variation' box is checked, the user can specify whether zero weights (if any) should be considered as random variables with zero mean by ticking the 'Variance on zero weights' box. If the box is left unchecked (default), then

Fig. 4. The FCM display plot and the hover functionality (green line), showcasing the FCM structure of the illustrative example in Section 3.

zero weights are assumed to indicate no connection between corresponding nodes. Next, the user can choose the parameter λ and the transfer function, which can be sigmoid or hyperbolic tangent. By default, the parameter λ is automatically selected by the application. Users can then submit their parameter preferences and FCM layout via the 'Execute simulation' button.

Based on the selected parameters and the 'fcm_layout_dict', the 'activation_function' module configures the transfer function, while the 'fcm_layout_parameters' module returns the weight matrix, lag matrix, and lambda parameter. The results of these modules are then fed into the 'fcm_object' module which processes all data in a consistent 'FCMap' object that is then run by the 'fcm_simulator' module.

FCM simulation

Based on bounds proposed for guaranteed convergence [19,20], In-Cognitive builds on a certain value for the parameter λ , $\hat{\lambda}$ hereafter, which is related to the FCM layout and specifically to the weight matrix [21]. The selection of $\hat{\lambda}$ guarantees that the FCM converges to a unique fixed point (e.g., Banach's fixed point [37,38]), the values of which depend on the existence of input/steady nodes—i.e., nodes that influence but are not influenced by other nodes and therefore remain always constant during FCM iterations. When there exist no input/steady nodes, the FCM converges to a specific fixed point regardless of the initial values of all nodes. For example, for FCMs simulated with the hyperbolic tangent transfer function (Eq. (3)), Banach's fixed point is always the zero point [39]; however, in the case of FCMs with input/steady nodes [21], the final node values are affected by the initial values of the input/steady nodes.

In conjunction with the convergence criterion, $\hat{\lambda}$ is selected such that it forces all arguments and the corresponding A_i^f values to fall within the 'almost-linear' region of the transfer function to obtain sufficient distance among nodes' final values [21]. However, this application-specific $\hat{\lambda}$ is typically small, yielding constrained final values A_i^f through Eq. (1). Consequently, the ranking of A_i^f values, which is the end goal of the FCM simulation, is hardly distinguished, hindering the process of extracting inferences from the simulation. To tackle this issue, a normalisation procedure has been proposed [22], spanning the A_i^f values analogously back to the $[0, 1]$ or $[-1, 1]$ interval for the case of sigmoid and hyperbolic tangent function, respectively. In doing so, it is possible to guarantee convergence using parameter $\hat{\lambda}$ and get distinguishable results. If A_i^f is the value of node C_j before the

normalisation process, then \hat{A}_i^f is the final value of node C_j after normalisation, based on the sigmoid (Eq. (4)) or the hyperbolic tangent transfer function (Eq. (5)).

$$\hat{A}_i^f = A_i^f + (0.09\lambda_s)x_i^f, \quad (4)$$

$$\hat{A}_i^f = 1.733A_i^f. \quad (5)$$

where x_i^f is the final value of the argument of Eq. (1).

The simulation stops either right after the number of iterations is greater than the maximum iterations defined by the user in the GUI (Fig. 2) or at an iteration where there is convergence for all nodes (i.e., the difference of two consecutive state vectors is smaller than an error threshold of 0.0001). Fig. 5 summarises these simulation steps.

It is noted that In-Cognitive does not provide the option for the user to select which nodes should converge nor to decide on the convergence threshold. Instead, the software guarantees that all nodes are converging, which is a necessary compromise for the integration of the MC simulation on top of the FCM analysis (see section below).

MCFCM simulation

In case of MC uncertainty, the 'fcmmc_object' and 'fcmmc_simulation' modules are used on top of the 'fcm_object' and 'fcm_simulator'. To integrate the MC procedure to the FCM simulation, a brute-force procedure is introduced to derive the impact of uncertainty propagation through the simulated system (see [33]).

Both inputs and weights can be sources of uncertainty and, therefore, the MC procedure can be applied for both. The simulation is executed N times by iteratively generating sample sets of the inputs vector and/or weights vector, leading to a distribution for each element of the output vector. The ensemble of output vectors is then used to derive the histograms of the output random variables. The greater the N , the closer these histograms are to the actual distributions of the elements of the output vector.

To generate vector samples, In-Cognitive employs the Beta distribution, as it is supported on a bounded interval. The original Beta distribution support is $[0, 1]$, which is suitable for the input values when the sigmoid transfer function is used. However, when the hyperbolic tangent transfer function is used, which means that the input values lie within $[-1, 1]$, the support of the Beta distribution is extended to $[-1, 1]$, and the same must be done for the weights. To adjust the Beta distribution to the $[-1, 1]$ range, In-Cognitive divides its argument with 0.5 and then subtracts one from this value.

If the inputs are variable and the weight matrix is constant, parameter $\hat{\lambda}$ remains constant per iteration. However, if the weights are also considered sources of uncertainty, parameter $\hat{\lambda}$ would change per iteration, violating the principle of MC procedure that the system must retain its layout per iteration. To tackle this issue, In-Cognitive introduces a new parameter $\hat{\lambda}_{MC}$, which is derived from the extreme case of assuming $|w_{ij}| = 1$, except for weights referring to non-existent FCM edges. Building on Koutsellis et al. [21], $\hat{\lambda}_{MC} \leq any \hat{\lambda}, \forall w_{ij} \in [-1, 1]$, to guarantee that all MC iterations reach a definite solution, and that the simulation does not stop without yielding results.

Results plotting

After the simulation is completed, the GUI alerts the user and presents the results on the 'Results' panel (Fig. 2). In these plots, the y-axis corresponds to the node names and the x-axis to the node values. The results of simulating the network without variation is presented with red dots. In case of a MCFCM simulation, the shape of distribution for each node is presented with a pale blue colour on top of the red dots.

Fig. 5. The FCM simulation procedure.

Configuration settings for the MCFCM analysis:

- Input nodes variation
 - Number of MC iterations (variable inputs): 2000
 - Standard deviation (variable inputs): 0.1
- Weights variation
 - Number of Monte Carlo iterations (variable weights): 1
 - Standard deviation (variable weights): 0.1
 - Variance on zero weights?
- Autoselect lambda?
 - Set lambda value: 0.1
 - Transfer function: hyperbolic

Execution ended successfully. Execute simulation

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Fig. 6. Illustrative example: (a) configuration settings and MCFCM results for (b) input nodes, (c) intermediate nodes, and (d) output nodes.

3. Illustrative example

In this section, we provide an illustrative example of the In-Cognitive application by running an MCFCM analysis on an FCM model sourced from Nikas et al. [1]. This model has been built to examine the diffusion of new solar power in Greece, considering implementation risks and long-term socioeconomic and macroeconomic impacts. The input nodes of this model consist of different policies and risks; intermediate nodes correspond to concepts that relate to solar power diffusion, such as components of the energy system in Greece; and output nodes include relevant impacts, such as electricity costs. Through In-Cognitive, it was possible to compare the results of the initial FCM analysis with the results of an MCFCM analysis (Fig. 6), evaluating the impact of parametric uncertainties on model outcomes as well as showcasing the usability of the software.

Initially, the authors replicated the FCM layout from Nikas et al. [1] in the Excel spreadsheet shown in Fig. 3. The spreadsheet was then uploaded to In-Cognitive and resulted in the FCM network seen in Fig. 4. The configuration options for the MCFCM analysis were then set as shown in Fig. 6a. For this example, we only included variation in the input nodes, while the MC simulation consisted of 2,000 iterations and the lambda parameter was automatically defined by the back-end code. Based on this configuration and input, the analysis is performed by pressing the 'Execute simulation' button. During this process, the most time-consuming step is developing the layout of the model in the input spreadsheet, as configuring and running the simulation takes minimal time.

Fig. 6b–d show the results of the analysis. The red dots show the value of the simple FCM analysis for each node, which coincide with the results from Nikas et al. [1]. The pale blue shades indicate the standard deviation for each node value, calculated

through the MCFCM and demonstrating how input uncertainty propagates through FCM nodes. It should be noted that the standard deviation is not the same for all nodes, as shown by the different shapes of distributions in the figures. For instance, the output nodes C29 (Employment) and C27 (Economic growth in long-term) have almost zero standard deviation, suggesting a potential dampening of the uncertainty coming from the inputs. In contrast, standard deviation is much higher for nodes C26 (Electricity costs for end-users) and C30 (Tariff deficits), to the point that it leads to both positive and negative values. This indicates that the influence of uncertainties in input policies and risks can lead to ambiguous impacts in these nodes, with significant implications to the conclusions of the analysis. Overall, the results of this case study show that In-Cognitive can provide analysts with an easy interface to quickly run an FCM model and receive useful indications on the robustness of their results through MCFCM.

The case study files are also available as an example in the GitHub repository.

4. Impact

The novelty of In-Cognitive lies in two main aspects: (1) the auto-selection of lambda parameter that guarantees that the FCM execution will always yield definite outcomes and (2) the integration of the MC procedure to the FCM simulation. The former, can help FCM analysts reach conclusions even in cases of chaotic FCM behaviour due to limitations and default values in the selection of the lambda parameter. The latter, helps analysts to explore the robustness of FCM outputs. In that way, In-Cognitive can potentially expand the applicability of the FCM methodology in multiple other problems and domains, allowing modellers to analyse systems with significant uncertainties in both FCM structure and inputs. For instance, the authors have successfully used In-Cognitive to evaluate the impacts of electricity prices in Europe, a highly uncertain parameter during the 2022 energy crisis, on the decarbonisation strategy of Italy [35] and Greece [34].

All this analysis is performed with an interactive and user-friendly GUI which could be further improved, as the In-Cognitive is open source and welcoming contributions from researchers around the world. User friendliness is also ensured by the fact that users do not need to install anything on their computer. A conventional browser is sufficient to interact with the GUI and exchange data with the back-end code. The MCFCM can provide results in less than a minute for a conventional FCM layout of thirty nodes and an MC simulation of 5000 iterations, giving an analyst the opportunity to explore the behaviour of larger and more complex FCM systems. Additionally, this simulation speed makes In-Cognitive ideal for live workshops, allowing analysts to run different variations of an FCM model based on interactive feedback from workshop participants (e.g., see [34]). Finally, while creating a model requires expertise in FCM methodology, simulating a model in In-Cognitive does not require any additional knowledge (for instance in programming), further increasing the usability of FCM methods, especially among new analysts.

5. Conclusions

This paper presents the In-Cognitive software application, an open-source, web-based application for the design and simulation of Fuzzy Cognitive Maps, including an integrated uncertainty analysis procedure based on Monte Carlo. Apart from the ability to examine the robustness of FCM results through the MC uncertainty analysis, In-Cognitive also features an algorithm for the selection of the lambda parameter, ensuring that the simulation

will always reach a definite solution and, therefore, all potential inputs can be included in an FCM model. In-Cognitive can be used in all decision-making applications that can be benefitted by the development of an FCM model, including energy planning, climate policy, and investment portfolio analysis. From a technical perspective, future development may focus on: (1) allowing exports of Monte Carlo simulation datasets (i.e., providing detailed outputs for all MC iterations upon user request); (2) configuring the FCM layout using input files in open-source formats such as csv; (3) integrating back-casting in FCM simulations; and (4) considering different standard deviations per node or edge. Moreover, since Bokeh has limitations on how the *networkX* Python library layouts are represented, In-Cognitive can currently represent maps only on a circular layout. Open-source alternatives to the Bokeh library or extra Bokeh widgets may be pursued, enabling the visualisation of nodes' self-loops – where relevant – as well as visualisation layouts other than circular and allowing the user to interactively adapt visualisation, e.g., in terms of the position, shape, size, and colour of nodes and edges. For instance, visualisation metaphors could be used to improve the cognitive clarity of FCM visual representation [40–42]. From a methodological perspective, the In-Cognitive application could be integrated to frameworks that couple FCM theory with timeseries forecasting [43,44]. Additionally, acknowledging that weight uncertainty cannot always be captured by random variables leading to the so-called fuzzy grey cognitive maps [45], interval uncertainty of weights could be introduced in a future version of the application to enable computation with intervals [46].

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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